

Cause-agnostic bridge damage state identification utilising machine learning

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ABSTRACT

The existing bridge stock, both in the EU and globally, contains several bridges that are reaching the end of their design-life, many of them showing signs of deterioration. Although different deterioration mechanisms are involved in this process, the dominant one is deemed to be the corrosion of tendons. As tendons are not always accessible, their state cannot be interpreted without invasive inspections, thus rendering the structural integrity assessment of bridges with corroded tendons an exceptionally challenging problem. Bridge deterioration is frequently expressed by visible permanent deflections that, however, cannot be interpreted into damage in a straightforward engineering manner due to their cause-agnostic nature. In response to this problem, a new data-driven approach is offered to facilitate a first-order bridge damage state assessment. With the proposed framework one can focus on the end result of the deterioration mechanism that is manifested on the bridge with vertical deck drifts and link these drifts to certain damage levels, which are invaluable in the context of bridge adaptation. An actual balanced cantilever bridge, located in the North-West part of Greece, experiencing large deflections in its balanced cantilever part, is employed to demonstrate the proposed methodology. The methodology involves the use of a finite element model of the bridge to investigate the effect of tendon loss on its structural integrity. Characteristic concrete Young's modulus values and plausible damage patterns on the prestressing tendons are considered to account for tendon loss and creep effects. A dataset of structural responses is numerically generated, and drift-based fragility functions are obtained. Exploiting the dataset of structural responses developed, the k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN) machine learning algorithm is then deployed to rapidly identify the damage state of bridges that would otherwise require thorough inspections and testing. The input required for the identification of the bridge damage state is only the observed deflected shape and the measured concrete Young's modulus. Thus, the significance of the proposed methodology is its ability to interpret vertical deck deflections, associated with tendon loss, into a bridge damage level, invaluable to decisions toward bridge retrofitting and adaptation.

1. Introduction

Over the past 50 years, the balanced cantilever construction method has become popular in bridge construction as it was proven to be a structurally effective and economically sound solution for the case of medium spans, i.e., approximately 100 to 200 m. However, it is nowadays evident that long-term effects on materials, such as creep and shrinkage of concrete (e.g., [1]) as well as corrosion (e.g., [2]) and

relaxation of steel tendons, can result in deck damage. The latter is manifested by excessive vertical deflections at the cantilever ends, an effect that has been reported since the 90's by several researchers (e.g., [3–5]). Numerous cases of bridge deterioration leading to excessive deflections have been documented in the past [6], with the severity of the damage in some cases extending well beyond serviceability concerns. For instance, deterioration might lead to partial collapse of the structure [7], fatalities, increased wear on alternative routes, tourism

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Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed damage state identification methodology.

decline and political fallout [8]. Although the main damage-triggering causes are almost confirmed to be the long-term effects, these, along with the impact of the ever-increasing traffic loads [9–11], the potential constructability issues [12], the failure mechanisms as well as a streamlined method to identify them, are not yet well documented despite multiple research endeavours [13–15].

Assessing the structural health/damage state of critical structural assets is of paramount importance, especially in the era of climate change aggravated hazards and ageing infrastructure (e.g., [16–22]). This aspect becomes even more vital when it comes to bridge assets that represent contemporary keystones in transportation networks. This is because such assets often have very limited meaningful redundancy to accommodate potential structural damages and hence to continue functioning at acceptable disruption levels [21,23]. For instance, failure of a single half-joint in a Gerber-type bridge, due to e.g. corrosion of its reinforcement [24], instantly results in a catastrophic bridge span unseating and failure. Owing to the above, bridges in modern societies undergo constant, routine or post-event structural health monitoring [25] to verify their structural integrity and identify the most efficient proactive or reactive maintenance/restoration measures [26–30].

Monitoring is nowadays accomplished via utilising several different techniques and technological advancements. Those techniques and advancements may involve in-situ sensors, visual inspections, laboratory tests, as well as airborne or satellite means. Yet, regardless of the means to collect “forensic” data [31], the overall scope is to detect notable changes in the asset geometry and/or the mechanical properties of the construction materials. These are likely to undermine either the imminent integrity of the structural asset of interest or its future performance subject to a peril or to cascading hazardous events. Based on the above, the monitoring concept, although broad in scope and the available means, is rather straightforward. Nevertheless, matching the observations with specific structural health conditions, that will lead to well-informed maintenance and adaptation action plans, is far from being a trivial task [32,33], quite the opposite in terms of time and costs. This perhaps excludes the two extreme conditions, i.e., (i) the unchanged status from the “as built” condition, which lead to the “do nothing and implement routine maintenance” action plan, and (ii) the partial or global collapse state which can be readily identified and signals activation of the “closure and excessive repairs or demolition and

replacement” action plan. By contrast, any intermediate damage state, e.g. minor, moderate and extensive, or even the “imminent collapse”, often require a great deal of effort and expertise to interpret. Indeed, in many cases, the utilisation of a detailed finite element model of the asset might be required, which needs to be calibrated using system identification techniques prior to its use for assessing current and predicting future performance.

Furthermore, although technological advancements, engaging digital measurements and data from structural health monitoring and remote sensing are nowadays available, bridge failures are rarely prevented. The reasons mainly lie in (a) the long reaction time of stakeholders to take mitigation measures in accordance with the principles of intelligent maintenance [34] and in view of their long-term positive benefits [35], (b) the amount of digital data requiring considerable processing, in which latent damage might not be easy to trace and (c) the fact that, in many cases, bridge designs and drawings are not available to the asset assessors and hence the as-built condition and properties of the bridge are largely unknown. This is a capability gap and can only be filled with engineering judgment, meaningful data and evidence, to underpin crucial decision-making by transportation stakeholders and operators.

The state-of-the-art research is currently shifting the paradigm of bridge damage state identification towards structural health monitoring [36] aided by machine learning techniques (e.g., [37–40]). Depending on the structural typology investigated, they might require the implementation of complex model updating techniques (model-based methods) or rely damage prediction solely on high quality monitored data (data-driven methods) through the detection of vibration property changes or the utilisation of other damage indicators (vibration-based structural health monitoring [41]). However, these indicators are often sensitive to temperature [42] and operational parameters [43] or proven to be not so robust when measured in uncontrolled environments [44].

The lack of a standard approach for bridge damage state identification gave motivation to this paper to put forward a preliminary, yet robust solution. What is described in the proposed method is substantially faster and less expensive to the current state-of-practice that engages multiple on-site inspections and measurements. The methodology that is presented herein can be used for routine monitoring on either

Fig. 2. (a) Side view of the landmark Polyfytos bridge (Source: Kozanilife.gr) and (b) the northern part of the bridge with the cantilevers.

new or existing assets. It could be also utilised in cases where the fragile nature of the asset and the uncertainty revolving its structural integrity poses as a barrier to destructive testing (e.g., loading with heavy vehicle) and extensive sample collection (e.g., cores taken from the concrete deck). In addition to that, as the construction sector is slowly moving towards digitalisation, and extensive monitoring and perhaps the adaptation of new materials that have the potential to prolong the lifetime of assets (e.g., [45,46]), the proposed solution relies heavily on computer simulations and cutting-edge measuring tools such as drone-based photogrammetry [47] providing a cost- and time-efficient solution, while also complying with environmental concerns. Laser scanning technology is rising in popularity [48] and has been found to achieve highly detailed results, even in restricted periods of time [49].

This paper sheds light on the condition of bridges and assist in the interpretation of fragmented, yet crucial, data and evidence to inform optimised decision-making by the operator via a reliable, cost and time-efficient method. Of particular interest is also to enable stakeholders appreciate that an investment in tools, digital technologies, monitoring and adaptation today will pay off in the long-term through the enhanced resilience of the bridge asset [35,50]. The combination of monitored data and numerically evaluated bridge deflection curves may be considered as evidence that can drive the project engineers to make a more precise machine learning-assisted assumption about the bridge

faults. Numerous examples across literature show that a misconception of the failure source may lead to erroneous repair methods, resulting in more extensive damage and sometimes even partial collapse, e.g., the 1967 collapse of the Silver Bridge [51], the 1996 collapse of the Koror-Babeldaob Bridge [52] or the 2018 collapse of the Polcevera viaduct [53]. At the same time, the proposed methodology is both efficient in terms of time and cost, carries little to no carbon footprint and helps engineers make first-order decisions, while having very little or no physical interaction with the bridge.

2. Methodological framework

Fig. 1 outlines the main steps and logical sequence of the proposed damage state identification methodology. The first step is the identification of the case-study deteriorated bridge or an index bridge that is representative to a bridge class that has to be assessed, on account that vertical deflections have been detected or might be detected in the future in its deck. For the considered case-study bridge (i.e., the Polyfytos bridge), given that it was constructed several decades ago, collection of all needed data in the form of drawings and/or design calculation reports was not feasible. Hence, pertinent data were eventually gathered from multiple sources, and data gaps, such as missing prestressing drawings and incomplete information on the construction

Fig. 3. Point cloud model of the landmark Polyfytos bridge showing the three out of the total six cantilevers.

quality and sequence, were filled based on engineering judgement. A point cloud dataset was also generated by means of drone-based photogrammetry to facilitate accurate measurements of the bridge geometry, i.e., the length of the cantilever segments and depth of sections. The data were then utilised for the development of the finite element model that is representative to the “as-built” condition of the bridge asset.

Next, the finite element bridge model was further used to undertake parametric scenario-based analyses considering (a) multiple degrees of damage that was expressed in terms of tendon area loss at the different cantilever segments and (b) variable Young’s modulus for the concrete. The variations in the concrete Young’s modulus were considered for capturing the potential deterioration of the concrete in the deck sections over time, and, as it is discussed later on in this paper, is important input for correctly identifying the bridge damage state. The aforementioned variable conditions formulate an analysis matrix, the structural analysis results of which form a training set. For each bridge sample in the training set (i.e., a bridge representation with different assumptions made for its tendon area loss in the cantilever segments and its concrete Young’s modulus) the vertical deflections in three critical locations of the bridge cantilever segments were numerically evaluated.

Finally, the actual deflected shape of the bridge cantilever, e.g., monitored by means of drone-based photogrammetry in practical applications or in our theoretical study numerically evaluated considering bridge samples that are different from those of the training set, was matched with the bridge samples from the training set that best describe its deflected shape—thus reflecting a possible damage state—. This matching was accomplished by utilising the k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN) machine learning algorithm. In particular, the k-NN algorithm is fed with the monitored deflected shape of the bridge and a measured concrete Young’s modulus (or any other suitable set of influential input attributes). The algorithm then consequently returns back the closest/s bridge sample/s from the training set in terms of their deflected shape, for which the damage state (i.e., extent of tendon loss) is known. It should be noted that the development of the training set might require a number of iterations on account of the computed vertical deflections not covering the anticipated response of interest and the efficiency of the

machine learning algorithm to correctly identify the bridge damage state. Upon the completion of this process the decision makers may exploit the findings in damage state-informed action plans.

The proposed framework, that enables a first-order bridge damage state identification, is presented and discussed in detail, along with the pertinent theoretical background. Subsequently, the framework is applied to a real bridge that was found to experience excessive vertical deck deflections, mainly attributed to tendon losses. All comparisons in this study were made on the basis of numerical data (i.e., computed vertical deck drifts). Those data were obtained by initially utilising several finite element bridge model representations (of the same bridge but reflecting different damage scenarios) that formulate a training set. Next, additional bridge model variations, that simulate different possible health state conditions of the bridge under study, were also utilised to numerically evaluate their structural responses. In an actual application, the latter responses would have been obtained by monitoring. However, their numerical evaluation was necessary due to the lack of complete information regarding the actual condition of the tendons of the asset considered. That would have allowed us to utilise monitored drifts to make predictions for the extent of tendon damage and check their accuracy on the basis of inspection data. However, the approach adopted here enables a more extensive efficiency verification of the proposed framework.

3. The case study Polyfytos bridge

3.1. Overview

The landmark Polyfytos bridge (see Fig. 2a) was adopted in this research as a case-study to showcase the proposed methodology. Built in 1975 in the Municipality of Western Macedonia, Kozani, Greece, the bridge spans a total length of 1371 m, thus holding the record for the largest overall length in Greece at the time of its construction. The Polyfytos bridge has a mixed structural system. Specifically, its structural system consists of simply supported I-beams and cantilevers with variable cross-sections and variable pier sections. The balanced cantilever method was used to formulate part of the bridge, and in particular

Fig. 4. Cross sections of the deck box girder segments of the cantilever part of the bridge (a) at the support and (b) at the tip of the cantilever.

that was constructed in 1953, without any prior warning [57]. This is an issue that has even been observed in the early years following the construction of a bridge. For instance, in the case of the Mid-Bay bridge in Florida, several post-tensioned tendons were replaced due to corrosion-related concerns only after eight years of its operation [58].

4. The k-nearest neighbours (k-NN) classification method

The k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN) classification method is a machine learning algorithm that was first introduced by Fix and Hodges [59,60]. The k-NN can be used to classify a sample based on its distance from neighbouring samples [61]. The neighbouring samples belong to the so-called training dataset. To identify the k-closest training sample neighbours to an unclassified sample, one may estimate its distance (e.g., Euclidean) from them. The mathematical formulation for estimating the Euclidean distance is:

$$d_{x,y} = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (x_j - y_j)^2} \quad (1)$$

where, x_j is the j^{th} attribute of the classified sample, y_j is the j^{th} attribute of the unclassified sample, and N is the number of attributes that are being considered for classifying the sample. In this study, we have used four attributes for classifying the data points of interest (i.e., the Young's modulus E of the concrete and the three vertical drift "measurements" at characteristic intervals across the length of the bridge cantilever, at 7 m 17 m as well as its tip at 27 m from the edge of the pier, L_p).

The k-NN algorithm is relatively simple in its application, yet it was proven to deliver results of satisfactory accuracy compared to other more complex machine learning methodologies (e.g., [62]). To avoid unintentionally assigning different weights to the considered attributes which are being used for the classification, due to them having different actual magnitudes and/or value ranges, prior to computing the Euclidean distances all variables should be first normalised so that their values fall within the range of [0,1]. A normalisation approach that one may consider, is the *min-max* scaling, which could be performed using the following formula:

$$y_{\text{norm}} = \frac{y - y_{\text{min}}}{y_{\text{max}} - y_{\text{min}}} \quad (2)$$

where, y is the actual value of the attribute and y_{min} , y_{max} , are the minimum and the maximum values of the attribute, respectively.

Of great importance to the successful implementation of the k-NN algorithm is also the selection of an appropriate k value. The k value essentially denotes the number of the nearest neighbours that will be used during the decision-making process, i.e., the sample classification. Given that there is no standard statistical method for pre-selecting the most appropriate k value, the optimum selection may be considered by investigating the errors stemming from several choices (e.g., 1-NN 2-NN and 3-NN).

The k-NN algorithm is not restricted to the realm of identifying the nearest neighbours of an unclassified sample. Given that this classification is made based on the computation of the distance of this sample from those of the training set, the distance per se could be exploited for ranking the identified neighbours. Apparently, the smaller the distance of the unclassified sample from a training set sample, the more alike this is to the latter. Therefore, instead of just pointing out to the nearest neighbours, the characteristics of such a sample may be evaluated as the weighted product of the characteristics of its neighbours [63]. Herein, each bridge sample in the training set corresponds to a different damage pattern for the investigated bridge. Hence, once the closest neighbours to an unclassified sample are identified based on the selected attributes, one can then estimate its damage pattern based on a weighted product of the damage patterns of its neighbours. The weight of the k^{th} training sample w_k , could be estimated as the inverse of its Euclidean distance

from the query sample, normalised by the sum of the inversed Euclidean distances from the query sample of all the N considered nearest training samples (see Eq. 3):

$$w_k = \frac{\frac{1}{d_{x,y,k}}}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \frac{1}{d_{x,y,i}}} \quad (3)$$

The k-NN algorithm does not perform well with high dimensional inputs (the so-called "curse of dimensionality", e.g., [64,65]). Hence, the number of attributes upon which a query sample will be classified should carefully be selected.

For the developed methodology, the field data essentially forms the unclassified bridge sample for applying the k-NN algorithm and finding its nearest neighbours from the training set. What remains unknown once we determine its neighbours is the damage pattern of such a sample (i.e., the actual bridge condition). Owing to the above, this could be estimated as the weighted sum of the damage patterns of the identified neighbour samples from the training set.

It should be pointed out that in the literature several different machine learning algorithms are available, e.g., artificial neural networks and random forests. These could potentially outperform the use of k-NN in the bridge damage state identification task that was addressed herein, e.g., [40,66,67]. Yet, an elaborate comparison of the alternative machine-learning methodologies remains out of the scope of this study. The focus is mainly in showcasing how a robust training dataset could be numerically generated for use in practical bridge health monitoring applications to pair observed vertical deck displacements with different damage states. The selection of the k-NN for undertaking this task is justified in view of its simplicity that is suitable for efficiently treating a problem of relatively low dimensionality.

5. Finite element modelling

The finite element model of the case-study bridge was developed in such a manner that the analysis process would resemble the actual construction process. The segmental construction of a balanced cantilever is an iterative process including a casting concrete stage followed by a prestressing stage upon the concrete reaching the desired strength. Hence, in an endeavour to create a model that depicts the actual construction sequence, the concrete segments were initially assigned a zero self-weight and a negligible bending stiffness. Then incrementally, one by one, were assigned their actual properties to eventually simulate each construction stage [68]. By contrast, the elements representing the tendons could be inserted at a specific construction stage.

Hence, initially a "soft" material was created and assigned to all segments except for the first two (construction stage 1). During the next step of the analysis, the first two segments were post-tensioned by tendons through inserting to the model the appropriate elements (construction stage 2). Following the post-tensioning of the first two segments, the next set is "casted", i.e., the Young's modulus and the self-weight of the concrete were restored to their actual values (construction stage 3). An iterative process, alternating concrete casting and post-tensioning phases, is then followed until all 16 segments (8 per cantilever at each side of the pier) are inserted to the model. At this point, the only load that was present on the girder was the self-weight of the prestressed segments. In the following step, the remaining external loads were applied. A pre-cast girder, represented by a load of 7200 kN on each side of the cantilever, was applied on the deck followed by the application of a uniform distributed load of 2 kN/m² that accounts for the asphalt layers, sidewalks etc. It should be noted that no traffic loads were applied on the model, and hence all associated deflections are not considered.

The material properties used in the finite element model were extracted from the original design report of the bridge. It should be noted that their actual properties do not match those of contemporary

Table 1
Material properties of the case-study bridge.

Material mentioned in the design report	Assumed material properties
Reinforced concrete B450	Young's modulus $E =$ varies across the samples of the training set from 10 – 35 GPa Compressive strength $f_{ck} = 40$ MPa Tensile strength $f_{ctm} = 3.5$ MPa Ultimate strain $\epsilon_{cu1} = 3.5$ ‰
Prestressing steel 160/180	Young's modulus $E_s = 195$ GPa Tensile strength $f_{pk} = 1770$ MPa 0.1 % proof stress $f_{p0.1k} = 1570$ MPa
Passive reinforcement St III	Yield strength $f_{yk} = 500$ MPa Strain at maximum force $\epsilon_{uk} = 2.5$ ‰

materials for which data is readily available, and hence several assumptions were made (see Table 1). The variation of the concrete modulus of elasticity of this paper reflects the Young's modulus of the concrete grade obtained by the original design report. Also, two lower values of Young's modulus were considered in the development of the training set to account for moderate and severe deterioration of the concrete material, in view of the adverse impact of creep on the modulus of elasticity [69].

The numerical model is mainly composed of 3D solid elements (see Fig. 6). A total of 14500 8-node isoparametric hexahedral elements with an 8-point integration scheme were utilised. A total of 4882 1D elements were used for modelling the tendons (see Fig. 7). The nonlinear behaviour of the concrete is captured via a plastic-fracture model. In this material model the fracture mode utilised the crack band model based on fracture energy and smeared crack formulation ([70,71]). This model employs the Rankine failure criterion. The hardening/softening plasticity model is based on the Menetrey-Willam [72] failure surface. The model utilised is deemed suitable for simulating concrete cracking, crushing under high confinement, and crack closure due to crushing in other material directions [73]. Both geometrical and material

nonlinearities were considered in the analyses. It should be noted that the pier supporting the balanced cantilevers was not explicitly modelled. This was deemed to be a reasonable simplification on account that the integrity of the foundation was not questioned, following preliminary survey investigations on the case study bridge. Hence, the cantilever segments at the location of the pier were assumed to be fixed at their bases.

It also worth noting that creep of concrete, which could be associated with large long-term deflections (e.g., [6,74]) that increase rapidly at the early years following the construction and at a slower rate afterwards, was not explicitly modelled in this study. Instead, creep was implicitly considered in the development of the training set, through including in the set bridge samples with lower Young's modulus (i.e., 10 and 20 GPa). Those reduced moduli of elasticity reflect reductions in the Young's modulus of concrete due to creep (e.g. [75]). This simplified one-step evaluation aligns with the scope of the proposed assessment methodology. This is because a more elaborate modelling of the time-dependent material properties to capture concrete creep, concrete shrinkage and cable relaxation (e.g., [76,77]) by utilising more detailed creep prediction models that are offered in the literature would have:

(a) required substantial effort with several repetitions of complex creep analyses for all the bridge model variations, over a period of 50 years, that formulate the training set; that is not justified within the context of the proposed assessment method and,

(b) rendered the estimated deck drifts of the training set samples time-dependent and hence the applicability of the set is limited only to the time assumed for evaluating the creep deflections.

Furthermore, the available prediction models are subject to various uncertainties ([78,79]) and in several cases they provide variable predictions [80]. On account of the above, the assessment of the analysed bridge in the proposed framework is based on measured deck drifts and a measured Young's modulus obtained at the time of the assessment. Thus, the predictions of the damage state of the bridge are made by pairing the measured drifts with the numerically evaluated ones,

Fig. 6. Isoparametric view of the finite element model of the case-study bridge (cantilevers at both sides of the pier are shown). The different colours signify the transition to a different segment of the cantilever (adopted from [55]).

Fig. 7. Global view of the tendons as located in the box girder sections of the cantilever segments (adopted from [55]).

prioritising the bridge samples of the training set with the closest Young's modulus to that measured.

6. Tendon loss pattern

To simplify the problem at hand and given the uncertainty with regards to the anchorage location of the tendons, the cantilever part of the bridge (beyond the edge of the pier) was subdivided in three Zones, each consisting of two segments. Hence, Zone 1 is formulated from segments S2 and S3, Zone 2 from segments S4 and S5 and Zone 3 from segments S6 and S7 (see Fig. 5). Furthermore, Zone 3 is supported by the Tendon 7 set (i.e., one Tendon 7 at each side of the box girder) and the Tendon 6 set. In fact, S7 is only supported, as per the assumptions made for the anchorage locations of the tendons and for the strands comprising each tendon (i.e., 7 strands), by the Tendon 7 set (i.e., 2 tendons \times 7 strands = 14 strands) while S6 is supported by the Tendon 6 and the Tendon 7 set (i.e., 4 tendons \times 7 strands = 28 strands). Essentially, in the event that Tendon 7 set is severely damaged, the structural integrity of S7 is directly undermined, whereas for S6 there is some level of indeterminacy since it is also supported by the Tendon 6 set. Yet, to simplify the tendon loss scenarios, both damage levels for the tendons that are anchored within the same Zone and losses for the same set of tendons at both sides of the concrete box cross section of the deck, were assumed uniform. For instance, if Tendon 6 set losses 60 % of its area due to corrosion, this will occur at both tendons that form the set and the same percentage will be assumed for the Tendon 7 set, since both of them are anchored within the same Zone. Consequently, in this study, the percentage that is reported for each Zone essentially denotes the loss of prestressing in this Zone considering all the tendons that are crossing the said Zone.

Apparently, no damage could be reported in the tip Zone 3 without having some sort of damage in Zones 1 and 2, simply because the two tendon sets that are present in Zone 3 are crossing from the other two preceding Zones. To put it otherwise, one may assume that each Zone is supported by four tendons (i.e., two tendon sets) that are directly anchored within its boundaries as well as by any other tendons that pass through it. Hence, if one considers a percentage loss of 33/21/14 % for Zones 1, 2 and 3, respectively this is essentially translated to 14 % loss of prestressing in the Tendon 6 and 7 sets. In particular, the 14 % amounts for a loss of one strand for each one of the four 7-strand tendons of Zone 3, since there are a total of $4 \times 7 = 28$ strands that support this Zone and $14 \% \times 28 \approx 4$ strands, hence 1 strand from each tendon. Moving on to Zone 2, we have Tendon 4 and 5 sets that are directly anchored within this Zone and Tendon 6 and 7 sets crossing it. To translate the 21 % of tendon losses, one first needs to evaluate how many strands are directly anchored or passing through this Zone. For Zone 2 there are 8 tendons (i.e., 4 tendon sets) \times 7 strands = 56 strands. Hence, the 21 % tendon loss translates to $21 \% \times 56 \approx 12$ damaged strands, of which four strands are related to the damage already reported for the tendon sets that are directly anchored in Zone 3 and the remaining 8 concern the two tendon sets that are anchored within Zone 2 (hence from each one of the four tendons that are directly anchored within Zone 2 a total of two strands is assumed to be fully corroded). The same principles apply for interpreting the damage in Zone 1. In this case, there are two tendon sets (Tendon 2 and 3) that are directly anchored within this Zone and Tendon 4, 5, 6 and 7 sets crossing it. Consequently, for Zone 1 there are 12 tendons (i.e., 6 tendon sets) \times 7 strands = 84 strands that support the Zone. A 33 % loss ratio means that $33 \% \times 84 \approx 28$ strands were damaged in this Zone. We have evaluated before that, the tendons directly anchored in Zone 3 have lost a total of 4 strands whereas the tendons that are anchored in Zone 2 have lost a total of 8 tendons. Hence, for the two tendon sets that are directly anchored within Zone 1, a total of $28 - 4 - 8 = 16$ strands are corroded. Given that a total of 4 tendons are directly anchored within Zone 1, each tendon from the 2nd and the 3rd Tendon sets should be damaged by a total of 4 strands.

7. Tendon loss scenarios

To simulate the steel corrosion effects on the strands, the investigated bridge was analysed multiple times assuming different percentages for the steel area losses within the worst affected zone. The steel area losses in the remaining two zones (i.e., those other than the worst affected) also varied as per the considered corrosion intensity scenarios. These scenarios may account for: (a) abrupt partial loss of the prestressing tendons due to excessive loads (tendon snap), and/or (b) fatigue and other long-term factors leading to gradual prestressing loss and/or (c) high degree of corrosion in the prestressing tendons. The adopted corrosion modelling approach by reducing the steel cross-sectional area of the tendons is deemed to be a reasonable simplification for developing the damage scenarios of interest. Other possible adverse corrosion impacts, such as for instance the reduction of the steel strength and ductility [10,81,82], could have an impact on the bridge performance, but are not captured by the reduction of the steel cross-sectional area. The latter though is likely to affect the integrity of the bridge, leading to more brittle failure modes either under extreme loads, that are not investigated herein, or in severe damage states where the steel tendons enter the inelastic range under normal loading conditions.

The tendon loss scenarios (i.e., damage patterns and concrete Young's modulus pairs) were selected exercising a great deal of engineering judgement so as to represent characteristic and likely cases for the investigated bridge. Apparently, for different bridge configurations or bridge classes, one may select other damage cases (e.g., different tendon loss ratios, nonuniform tendon loss ratios between the mirror segments at the two sides of the balanced cantilever) to formulate the training set and consider also other failure mechanisms (e.g., rotation at the piers due to scour). However, given the evidence from the preliminary inspections on the case study bridge only tendon loss scenarios were considered herein. The idea behind the formulation of those scenarios is to include as many likely cases of damage patterns as possible. It was also intended to account for those uncertain factors that are likely to severely impact the performance of the bridge for a certain or a spectrum of failure mechanisms. However, it should be noted that different failure mechanisms that have similar adverse effects on the bridge (e.g., downward vertical displacements) may need to be treated by separate training sets and not necessarily lumped to a single one.

Herein, concrete deterioration was identified as an influential factor of uncertainty, and for this reason each tendon loss sample was analysed for three different Young's modulus values. In real applications, field and laboratory tests may provide estimates for the actual value of an input parameter at the time of the training set generation. In this case, variations of this parameter may be omitted from the considered plausible damage scenarios. This parameter, however, should remain relatively constant for the timeframe of interest, otherwise the use of the training set to assess the damage state of the bridge will become obsolete in the future. It should be noted that the developed scenarios are not exhaustive. However, the scope of this research study is to showcase the applicability of the proposed methodology. There is also always the possibility to use independently different scenarios that reflect different possible failure mechanisms for the same bridge. This process could either provide multiple predictions if limited or zero information is available at the time of assessment or allow for the selection of the most appropriate training set in view of preliminary observations made by inspecting the structure. For instance, in the event that in-situ investigations reveal scour at the piers, alternative scenarios should be considered.

On the aforementioned basis, the tendon loss scenarios were formulated considering 27 representative damage patterns (tendon loss % for each one of the three bridge Zones) for three different concrete Young's modulus (i.e., 10, 20 and 35 GPa). The assumed tendon loss damage patterns are presented in Table 2. This approach essentially yielded a dataset with $3 \times 27 = 81$ bridge samples (i.e., 27 bridge

Table 2
Percentage of tendon loss in each one of the bridge zones for the 27 scenarios that were considered per concrete Young' modulus and three corresponding bridge damage states.

Case	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Case	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3
Case 1 (M)	19 %	0 %	0 %	Case 2 (M)	19 %	29 %	0 %
Case 3 (S)	19 %	29 %	57 %	Case 4 (M)	33 %	21 %	14 %
Case 5 (S)	33 %	43 %	57 %	Case 6 (M)	33 %	43 %	29 %
Case 7 (S)	48 %	43 %	29 %	Case 8 (S)	48 %	43 %	57 %
Case 9 (S)	48 %	57 %	57 %	Case 10 (M)	24 %	0 %	0 %
Case 11 (M)	24 %	36 %	0 %	Case 12 (C)	24 %	36 %	71 %
Case 13 (M)	43 %	29 %	29 %	Case 14 (C)	43 %	50 %	71 %
Case 15 (S)	43 %	50 %	29 %	Case 16 (S)	57 %	50 %	29 %
Case 17 (C)	57 %	50 %	71 %	Case 18 (C)	57 %	71 %	71 %
Case 19 (M)	29 %	0 %	0 %	Case 20 (M)	29 %	43 %	0 %
Case 21 (C)	29 %	43 %	86 %	Case 22 (S)	52 %	36 %	29 %
Case 23 (C)	52 %	64 %	86 %	Case 24 (S)	52 %	64 %	43 %
Case 25 (C)	71 %	64 %	43 %	Case 26 (C)	71 %	64 %	86 %
Case 27 (C)	71 %	86 %	86 %				

models with different tendon loss damage intensities in each zone and 3 different concrete Young's modulus) for which the drift profiles were evaluated by means of finite element analyses. Then it was assumed that during an inspection of the actual bridge, the engineers will measure the deflections at characteristic locations as well as determine the concrete Young's modulus.

The finite element model of the case-study bridge that was discussed

in a previous section (see Fig. 6 and Fig. 7), was utilised for obtaining the downward vertical drifts at three characteristic locations along the cantilever (i.e., at 10, 20 and 30 m from the pier centreline or 7, 17 and 27 m from the edge of the pier) for the bridge samples that formulate the training set. Fig. 8 illustrates the downward vertical displacement (d_v) and drift ratio (VDR) profiles for all 81 (=27 × 3) bridge samples. The VDR is computed by dividing the vertical displacement measured at a certain point of the deck with the distance of this point from the edge of the pier support. As can be inferred from Fig. 8, there are at least 3 samples (tendon damage patterns) in each Young's modulus set which exhibit notable higher drifts at the tip of the cantilever. As expected, Case 27 (see Table 2), that corresponds to a damage scenario with severe tendon losses across all segments of the cantilever including its tip, results in the maximum computed vertical drifts for the tip of the cantilever irrespectively of the concrete Young's modulus.

8. Damage states

Damage states (e.g., [83]) are considered on account of the percentage of tendon losses in the worst damaged segment of the balanced cantilever. In the analyses to follow, the damage state (DS) was characterised as "Moderate" for tendon losses between 19–45 % in any segment of the cantilever, "Severe" for tendon losses between 46–65 % and "Critical" for tendon losses in any one segment in excess of 66 %. These percentages and their associated damage states are primarily based on expert judgement. The allocation of the training set bridge samples (corresponding to different tendon loss scenarios) to certain damage states was further checked considering the magnitude of the computed vertical deck deflections for those samples.

The characterisation of the DS of each sample of the training set is also shown in Table 2, with M, S and C denoting a Moderate, Severe and Critical damage state ds_i for the bridge, respectively. Hence, the training set for each concrete Young's modulus has 9 samples that correspond to a moderate bridge damage state, 9 samples that could be associated with a severe bridge damage state and 9 samples that reflect a critical bridge damage state. If any of the above ds_i is detected in a monitored bridge, further action is required in all cases, but the managing authority could

Fig. 8. Vertical displacement (top row) and drift profiles (bottom row) of the bridge cantilever for all samples that form the set of scenarios considering the three concrete Young's modulus variations.

Fig. 9. Drift-based fragility functions for the three considered DS and concrete Young's modulus.

take more informed decisions with regards to the emergency of the situation to undertake more thorough investigations, impose traffic control or speed restrictions or even close the bridge.

9. Drift-based fragility functions

On the basis of the maximum vertical drift (or displacements) ratios (VDR_{max} , i.e., the maximum vertical drift ratio over all segments) that were obtained for the training set samples as well as their assignment to specific damage state, one may also define drift-based fragility functions (e.g., [84]) for each ds_i . Those functions essentially provide the probability of reaching or exceeding a damage state given a certain level of maximum vertical drift ratio (or displacement). These fragility functions can be used for undertaking a performance-based evaluation of an asset bridge that belongs to the same class with the class bridge described by the training samples (i.e., reinforced concrete prestressed cantilever bridges with tendon losses as their predominant damage/failure mode). For each damage state (ds_i , i.e., M, S, C) the “empirical” fragility functions were obtained by first identifying the samples in the set for which the considered ds_i was observed. Then these samples should be sorted by means of their VDR_{max} in ascending order. Finally, the cumulative probability of being in this damage state may be evaluated as i/N , with i being the order of a specific sample and N being the total number of the samples from the training set that have been identified for being in a particular damage state. The latter essentially yields nine samples for each of the M, S and C damage states.

Further to the above, in order to compute the fragility functions the “empirical” cumulative functions were fitted using a log-normal distribution, which is commonly used in engineering applications (e.g., [85]), as follows,

$$P(DS \geq ds_i | VDR_{max}) = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(VDR_{max}) - \mu_{\ln(VDR_{max})}}{\sigma_{\ln(VDR_{max})}}\right) \quad (4)$$

where, $P(DS \geq ds_i | VDR_{max})$ is the conditional probability of reaching or exceeding a certain damage state ds_i at a specific VDR_{max} level, Φ is the cumulative standard normal distribution and $\mu_{\ln(VDR_{max})}$ and $\sigma_{\ln(VDR_{max})}$ are the central tendency and the standard deviation of the natural logarithms of the VDR_{max} for the samples of each damage state.

Fig. 9 illustrates for the three considered damage states and the three concrete Young's modulus the “empirical” cumulative distribution of the data along with the lognormal fitting. Apparently, the fitting at ds_3 improves substantially if one removes the outlier point at the upper tail of the fragility function (see the dashed line curve in Fig. 9). The same figure also presents the fragility functions for the three damage states considering the entire set of bridge samples (i.e., $3 \times 27 = 81$ samples, “all E”). Table 3 summarises the statistical parameters for the fitted lognormal distributions, i.e., the median VDR_{max} , \widehat{VDR}_{max} evaluated as the $\exp[\mu_{\ln(VDR_{max})}]$ as well as the $\sigma_{\ln(VDR_{max})}$.

As can be inferred by inspecting the drift-based fragility functions obtained for the different ds_i and for three different concrete Young's

Table 3

Statistical parameters estimated for the VDR_{max} -based lognormal fragility functions corresponding to the four ds_i and the three considered concrete Young's modulus. The estimates inside the parenthesis at ds_3 denote the statistical parameters disregarding the outlier vdr_{max} point.

ds_i	E [GPa]	\widehat{VDR}_{max} [%]	$\sigma_{\ln(VDR_{max})}$
$ds_1 = M$	10	0.091	0.22
$ds_2 = S$	10	0.138	0.28
$ds_3 = C$	10	0.197 (0.178)	0.47 (0.39)
$ds_1 = M$	20	0.048	0.31
$ds_2 = S$	20	0.095	0.27
$ds_3 = C$	20	0.147 (0.129)	0.55 (0.41)
$ds_1 = M$	35	0.038	0.41
$ds_2 = S$	35	0.076	0.21
$ds_3 = C$	35	0.136 (0.118)	0.61 (0.46)
$ds_1 = M$	All	0.055	0.49
$ds_2 = S$	All	0.100	0.35
$ds_3 = C$	All	0.158	0.55

modulus, those obtained for the lowest Young's modulus (i.e., $E = 10$ GPa) are less severe (i.e., lower probability of being or exceeding a damage state given a certain VDR_{max}) than their counterparts (i.e., those corresponding to the same damage state) for the highest Young's modulus. The physical interpretation of this is that at a given VDR_{max} level, if the less stiff structure (i.e., the one with the lowest Young's modulus) under identical loading conditions, deflects by the same amount compared to the stiff one, this essentially means that the tendons of the former are less damaged/corroded compared to the tendons of the stiffer bridge and due to this condition, the structure does not deflect more. In other words, the stiffer structure should have lost more of its prestressing capacity compared to the more flexible one if the structures deflect by the same amount under identical loading conditions.

Another important observation stems from inspecting the fragility functions obtained by considering the entire dataset (i.e., bridge samples from “all E”). In this case, the “all E” fragility functions, were found to have a median that is lower, given a damage state, than the median of the $E = 10$ GPa and higher for the remaining two E. This means that if the E is ignored in the definition of the fragilities, the induced bias could result in unconservative fragility estimates.

10. Damage state identification through k-NN

To test the efficiency of the k-NN algorithm towards identifying the nearest sample(s) from the training set (Fig. 8) that best reflect the actual damage pattern (i.e., the damage state of the bridge determined from the tendon losses in the worst affected zone) of a bridge for which the deflections and concrete Young's modules are known, five unclassified bridge samples were defined (see Table 4). Those unclassified samples essentially reflect actual bridges with either identical or similar influential characteristics (e.g., type of bridge, level of prestressing) to the bridge samples of the training set, so as one may rationally assume that they belong to the same bridge class ([86,87]). For each unclassified

Table 4

Damage state (% of tendon losses) and concrete Young’s modulus of the unclassified bridge samples.

Unclassified Sample (US)	Actual Damage Zone	Actual Damage Zone	Actual Damage Zone	E [GPa]
	1	2	3	
US1	43 %	50 %	29 %	18
US2	71 %	86 %	86 %	22
US3	71 %	64 %	43 %	30
US4	57 %	57 %	57 %	17
US5	48 %	43 %	14 %	25

sample, a tendon loss pattern and a concrete Young’s modulus was assumed. These properties were assigned to the bridge finite element model for estimating numerically the vertical drift ratios along the bridge cantilever (see Fig. 10). In actual practical applications, this procedure is redundant, since the drift profile of the investigated bridge could be determined via, for instance, drone-based photogrammetry and the concrete Young’s modulus via laboratory testing. Having obtained the drift profile of the bridge and the concrete Young’s modulus the question is whether the k-NN is an efficient methodology for identifying the damage state of the bridge, that in an actual investigation will be unknown and will require thorough investigation for being identified

Fig. 10. Numerically evaluated vertical drift profiles of the unclassified bridge cantilever samples of Table 4.

Table 5

Damage state (% of tendon losses per Zone) and damage state of the query bridge samples and the predictions of the k-NN algorithm, considering one, two and three neighbours as well as the predictions obtained via weighting the contribution of each neighbour by the inverse of the Euclidean distance.

Case	Actual damage per Zone [%] and actual ds	1-NN	2-NN	3-NN
US1	43/50/29 (S)	1st NN: 48/43/29 (S)	2nd NN: 48/43/57 (S)	3rd NN: 43/50/71 (C)
		Weighted: 48/43/29 (S)	Weighted: 48/43/43 (S)	Weighted: 46/45/52 (S)
US2	71/86/86 (C)	1st NN: 71/86/86 (C)	2nd NN: 71/86/86 (C)	3rd NN: 71/86/86 (C)
		Weighted: 71/86/86 (C)	Weighted: 71/86/86 (C)	Weighted: 71/86/86 (C)
US3	71/64/43 (C)	1st NN: 71/64/43 (C)	2nd NN: 71/64/86 (C)	3rd NN: 71/64/43 (C)
		Weighted: 71/64/43 (C)	Weighted: 71/64/62 (C)	Weighted: 71/64/58 (C)
US4	57/57/57 (S)	1st NN: 57/71/71 (C)	2nd NN: 71/64/43 (C)	3rd NN: 57/71/71 (C)
		Weighted: 57/71/71 (C)	Weighted: 64/68/57 (C)	Weighted: 62/62/62 (S)
US5	48/43/14 (S)	1st NN: 43/29/29 (M)	2nd NN: 33/43/29 (M)	3rd NN: 33/43/57 (S)
		Weighted: 43/29/29 (M)	Weighted: 38/36/29 (M)	Weighted: 37/38/38 (M)

Fig. 11. Deflections of the unclassified samples (US1-US5) along with the deflections and the concrete Young’s modulus of the three nearest neighbour samples.

Fig. 12. Confusion matrix assessing the accuracy of damage state identification considering (a) the 1-NN & 2-NN and (b) the 3-NN weighted predictions. The green colour is used for identifying the accurate predictions (true), while the grey colour the inaccurate ones.

(whereas herein it is known a priori and forms the basis of assessing the k-NN predictions). It should be noted that the damage patterns of the unclassified samples US1-US3 exist in the training test and those samples differ from those of the pertinent samples in the training set only by their concrete Young's modulus. When applying the k-NN algorithm all input data associated with the unclassified sample (i.e., drifts and concrete Young's modulus) should be within the limits of the pertinent training set data, since extrapolating beyond the considered ranges is not meaningful.

Fig. 11 and Table 5 summarise the NN to the unclassified samples along with the damage states that were determined by means of the k-NN algorithm. The k-NN algorithm was applied having considered one, two or three samples from the training set that are closer (in terms of the evaluated Euclidean distance) to each of the US summarised in Table 4. It should be noted that the accuracy of the training algorithm could be improved by increasing the size of the training set (i.e., account for more tendon loss damage patterns and a higher number of concrete Young's modulus). An increased training set and in general the development of the set needed in order to implement the proposed assessment framework later on in the lifetime of a bridge, requires less effort if it becomes a prerequisite of the initial design of every keystone asset. This is because all needed information, such as the construction drawings, along with the model of the bridge are readily available at that time.

As can be inferred by both inspecting Table 5 and the confusion matrices illustrated in Fig. 12, the utilisation of three nearest samples from the training set yields the highest percentage of accurate answers (i.e., highest tagging accuracy [88]). In particular, only one prediction out of the five is found to be inaccurate and less conservative (i.e., US assigned to a lower damage state than its actual one [89]). Yet, it should be noted that even in this case, the underestimation of the damage state of the bridge (i.e., bridge classified as being in a moderate damage state instead of the actual severe) occurs for an unclassified sample (US5) that marginally belongs to the severe damage state. For this unclassified sample the tendon loss percentage in one of its zones exceeds marginally the threshold of 45 % that signals the transition from the moderate damage state to the severe damage state. Both the weighted 1-NN and the weighed 2-NN, despite being less accurate than the 3-NN weighted classification, were able to correctly identify the damage state for three unclassified samples, while in one case the prediction was conservative (i.e., predicted damage state "Critical" in a case where the actual damage state is "Severe") and for the US5, similarly to the 3-NN, they underestimated the overall damage state.

11. Conclusions

A first-order damage state assessment methodology was proposed for the damage state identification of bridges with tendons that are corroded to an unknown extent. The proposed framework that exploits measured deck displacements in bridges and utilises the k-NN algorithm

was presented in this paper to identify the underlying damage. Utilising the dataset of vertical deflections that are numerically generated, fragility functions are offered that can also be used in the context of loss assessment methodologies, e.g., for large portfolios of bridges and for expedient decision making, when further investigations are pending toward designing adaptation measures. It was showcased that the developed methodology could successfully identify the damage state of a bridge for which the deflected shape and the concrete Young's modulus are determined. Hence, the proposed method could be exploited by engineers to make first-order decisions while having very little or no physical interaction with the bridge. The damaged states were defined considering the maximum percentage of tendon losses across the span of the balanced cantilever. Drift-based fragility functions were also developed to allow a probabilistic assessment of the level of damage that is experienced by a bridge should the Young's modulus of the concrete and the maximum vertical drift across the span of the cantilever are known. Fragility functions were also developed only as a function of the maximum vertical drift, but in this case the probability estimates of reaching or exceeding a given damage state are less accurate.

The proposed methodology could also accommodate deterioration mechanisms other than the tendon losses associated either with the deck component or with other bridge components (e.g., pier, bearing). Furthermore, the method could be used for other types of bridges, as well as adjusted to be applicable to other type of structures (e.g., buildings, retaining walls) in which monitoring could be utilised to measure variations in their deformations, rotations, accelerations and/or vibration characteristics. It could be also utilised for identifying which monitoring parameters are the most important ones for assessing the damage state of a civil structure.

The proposed methodology is suitable for a first-order damage state identification for large portfolios of bridges and for expedient decisions. Nevertheless, planning of restoration measures would require substantial investment in thorough inspections, investigations and testing to verify this method. Yet, the method can be utilised to make preliminary recommendations on account of the findings, for closing the bridge or reducing the speed and the weight of the crossing vehicles.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Athanasia Kazantzi: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sokratis Moutsianos:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Konstantinos Bakalis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Stergios-Aristoteles Mitoulis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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